

Chromosome 1

Chromosome 2

Chromosome 4

Chromosome 5

Chromosome 6

Chromosome 7

Chromosome 8

Chromosome 9

Chromosome 10

Additional file 3 (.pdf)

Figure S3: Variation of the markers density, the recombination rate and the genome coverage in non-overlapping 2 Mbp windows along each chromosome except chromosome 3 (presented in Figure 1). Markers have MAF above 5%. Top panel shows the variation of SNP number. In the bottom panel, dotted line represents the variation of recombination rate (cM / Mbp) and solid lines the proportion of genome covered by the SNPs using the cumulated length of physical LD windows around each SNP in each 2Mbp-windows. In these two panel, green, blue, red and black lines represent variation for GBS, 600K, 50K and combined technologies, respectively. Vertical dotted gray lines indicate limits of centromeric regions. Vertical lines between the two panels indicate the position of QTLs for flowering time (DTA), grain yield (GY) and Plant Height (PHT). Green, blue, red vertical lines indicate QTLs detected only by GBS, 600K and 50K technologies, respectively. Grey vertical lines indicate QTL detected by at least two technologies. Only QTL including a marker associated with $-\log_{10}(pval)$ above 6 were shown.